

MUSIQA DARSLARIDA INTERFAOL TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI.

Xudayberdiyeva Mushtariy, Qori Niyoziy nomidagi Tarbiya milliy pedagogika instituti 3 bosqich tayanch doktoranti, Toshkent, O'zbekiston

Annotatsiya

KIRISH: hozirgi globallashtirish va raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida ta'lim tizimida interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ayniqsa, musiqa ta'limida interfaol yondashuvlar o'quvchilarning faolligini oshirish, ularning ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantirish va bilimlarni samarali o'zlashtirishga xizmat qiladi. An'anaviy musiqa darslarida o'qituvchi markaziy rol o'ynagan bo'lsa, interfaol texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etilgan darslarda o'quvchi faol subyektga aylanadi. Bu esa musiqa darslarida nafaqat ijrochilik, balki tinglash, tahlil qilish va mustaqil fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish imkonini beradi.

MAQSAD: ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi – musiqa darslarida interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanishning nazariy va amaliy asoslarini chuqur o'rganish hamda ularning ta'lim samaradorligiga ta'sirini ilmiy jihatdan asoslashdan iborat. Shuningdek, tadqiqot quyidagi kengaytirilgan vazifalarni ham o'z ichiga oladi: Interfaol texnologiyalarning pedagogik va psixologik asoslarini aniqlash hamda ularning musiqa ta'limidagi o'rini belgilash; Musiqa darslarida qo'llaniladigan zamonaviy interfaol metodlar va vositalarning turlarini tizimli tahlil qilish; Interfaol texnologiyalarning o'quvchilarning bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarini shakllantirishdagi rolini aniqlash; O'quvchilarning ijodiy fikrlashi, musiqiy idroki va estetik dunyoqarashini rivojlantirishda interfaol yondashuvlarning ahamiyatini baholash; Interfaol texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etilgan darslarning o'quvchilar motivatsiyasi va faolligiga ta'sirini o'rganish; Musiqa ta'limida multimedia va raqamli vositalardan foydalanish samaradorligini aniqlash; An'anaviy va interfaol ta'lim usullarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish orqali eng samarali metodlarni aniqlash; O'qituvchilarning interfaol texnologiyalarni qo'llashdagi metodik tayyorgarligini baholash; Musiqa darslarida interfaol texnologiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish; O'quvchilarning mustaqil ishlash, musiqiy tahlil qilish va ijodiy faoliyatini rivojlantirishda interfaol muhitning rolini aniqlash.

MATERIALLAR VA METODLAR: ushbu tadqiqotda musiqa ta'limida interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanish samaradorligini aniqlash maqsadida kompleks yondashuv asosida turli didaktik va texnologik materiallardan foydalanildi. Jumladan, multimedia vositalari sifatida interaktiv taqdimotlar, audio va video yozuvlar, virtual darsliklar qo'llanildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida texnik jihozlar – kompyuter, planshet, interaktiv doska, proyektor va audio tizimlardan samarali foydalanildi. Shuningdek, turli janrdagi musiqiy asarlar, nota materiallari va partituralar asosiy o'quv materiallari sifatida xizmat qildi. Raqamli platformalar, xususan, onlayn ta'lim tizimlari va musiqiy ilovalar orqali o'quvchilarning mustaqil ishlash faoliyati tashkil etildi. Empirik materiallar sifatida

o'quvchilarning ijro yozuvlari, dars jarayonidagi kuzatuv natijalari hamda so'rovnoma ma'lumotlari tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqotda nazariy va amaliy metodlar uyg'un holda qo'llanildi. Nazariy tahlil metodi orqali interfaol texnologiyalar va musiqa pedagogikasiga oid ilmiy adabiyotlar o'rganildi. Eksperimental metod asosida o'quvchilar an'anaviy va interfaol metod asosida ta'lim oluvchi guruhlariga ajratilib, ularning bilim darajasi, faolligi va ijodiy ko'rsatkichlari qiyosiy tahlil qilindi. Pedagogik kuzatuv jarayonida o'quvchilarning darsdagi ishtiroki, musiqiy qiziqishi va ijodiy yondashuvi muntazam monitoring qilindi. Interfaol metodlar sifatida "aqliy hujum", "klaster", "insert", rol o'ynash, musiqiy improvizatsiya va guruhli ishlash usullari qo'llanildi. Diagnostik va baholash metodlari yordamida o'quvchilarning bilim, ko'nikma va malakalari testlar, ijro baholash mezonlari asosida aniqlab borildi. Bundan tashqari, so'rovnoma va intervyu metodlari orqali o'quvchilar hamda o'qituvchilarning fikrlari o'rganildi. Olingan natijalar statistik tahlil usullari yordamida umumlashtirilib, refleksiya metodi orqali o'quvchilarning o'z-o'zini baholash jarayoni ham tahlil qilindi.

MUHOKAMA VA NATIJALAR: tadqiqot natijalari quyidagilarni ko'rsatdi: Faollikning oshishi: interfaol texnologiyalar qo'llanilgan darslarda o'quvchilarning darsga qiziqishi va ishtiroki sezilarli darajada oshdi; Bilimlarning mustahkamligi: audio va vizual materiallar yordamida o'rganilgan mavzular uzoq muddatli xotirada saqlanadi; Ijodiy rivojlanish: interfaol mashg'ulotlar o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash, improvizatsiya va ijodiy yondashuvini rivojlantiradi; Hamkorlik ko'nikmalari: guruhli ishlash orqali o'quvchilar o'zaro muloqot va hamkorlikni o'rganadi. Shu bilan birga, interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanishda ayrim muammolar ham mavjud: texnik vositalarning yetishmasligi, o'qituvchilarning raqamli kompetensiyasining pastligi va vaqtni to'g'ri taqsimlash zarurati.

XULOSA: o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, musiqa darslarida interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanish ta'lim samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Interfaol yondashuvlar o'quvchilarning dars jarayonidagi faolligini kuchaytirib, ularning bilimlarni chuqur va mustahkam o'zlashtirishiga xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, multimedia vositalari va interaktiv metodlar orqali tashkil etilgan mashg'ulotlar o'quvchilarning musiqiy idroki, eshitish qobiliyati hamda ijodiy fikrlashini rivojlantirishda muhim omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, interfaol texnologiyalar o'quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash, muammoli vaziyatlarga ijodiy yondashish va o'z bilimlarini amaliyotda qo'llash ko'nikmalarini shakllantiradi. Guruhli ishlash va hamkorlikka asoslangan metodlar esa o'quvchilar o'rtasida kommunikativ kompetensiyalarni rivojlantiradi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni tasdiqlaydiki, interfaol metodlar asosida tashkil etilgan musiqa darslari an'anaviy darslarga nisbatan samaraliroq bo'lib, o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasi va qiziqishini oshiradi. Biroq, interfaol texnologiyalarni samarali qo'llash uchun o'qituvchilarning metodik tayyorgarligi, raqamli kompetensiyasi hamda texnik vositalar bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Shu sababli, ta'lim tizimida zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni joriy etish bilan bir qatorda, o'qituvchilarning malakasini oshirish va zarur texnik sharoitlarni yaratish zarur hisoblanadi. Umuman olganda, musiqa

ta'limida interfaol texnologiyalardan foydalanish o'quvchilarning har tomonlama rivojlanishini ta'minlovchi samarali pedagogik vosita sifatida e'tirof etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Interfaol texnologiyalar, musiqa ta'limi, kreativlik, multimedia, interaktiv metodlar, pedagogik samaradorlik.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА УРОКАХ МУЗЫКИ.

Худайбердиева Муштарий, базовый докторант 3 курса Национального педагогического института воспитания имени Кори Ниёзи, Ташкент, Узбекистан

Аннотация

ВВЕДЕНИЕ: в условиях современной глобализации и цифровой трансформации использование интерактивных технологий в системе образования приобретает особую значимость. Особенно в музыкальном образовании интерактивные подходы способствуют повышению активности учащихся, развитию их творческого мышления и эффективному усвоению знаний. Если в традиционных уроках музыки центральную роль играл преподаватель, то в условиях использования интерактивных технологий учащийся становится активным субъектом образовательного процесса. Это позволяет развивать не только исполнительские навыки, но и умения слушания, анализа и самостоятельного мышления.

ЦЕЛЬ: основная цель данного исследования заключается в углублённом изучении теоретических и практических основ использования интерактивных технологий на уроках музыки, а также научном обосновании их влияния на эффективность обучения. В рамках исследования поставлены следующие задачи: определение педагогических и психологических основ интерактивных технологий и их роли в музыкальном образовании; системный анализ современных интерактивных методов и средств, применяемых на уроках музыки; выявление роли интерактивных технологий в формировании знаний, умений и навыков учащихся; оценка значения интерактивных подходов в развитии творческого мышления, музыкального восприятия и эстетического мировоззрения; изучение влияния интерактивных технологий на мотивацию и активность учащихся; определение эффективности использования мультимедийных и цифровых средств в музыкальном образовании; сравнительный анализ традиционных и интерактивных методов обучения; оценка методической подготовки преподавателей к использованию интерактивных технологий; разработка научно-практических рекомендаций по их внедрению; а также определение роли интерактивной среды в развитии самостоятельной деятельности, музыкального анализа и творческой активности учащихся.

МАТЕРИАЛЫ И МЕТОДЫ: в данном исследовании для определения эффективности использования интерактивных технологий в музыкальном образовании применялся комплексный подход с использованием различных дидактических и технологических материалов. В частности, использовались мультимедийные средства: интерактивные презентации, аудио- и видеозаписи, виртуальные учебные пособия. В процессе исследования активно применялись технические средства – компьютер, планшет, интерактивная доска, проектор и аудиосистемы. В качестве учебного материала использовались музыкальные произведения различных жанров, нотные материалы и партитуры. С помощью цифровых платформ, включая онлайн-образовательные системы и музыкальные приложения, была организована самостоятельная деятельность учащихся. В качестве эмпирических данных анализировались записи исполнения учащихся, результаты педагогических наблюдений и данные анкетирования. В исследовании были применены как теоретические, так и практические методы. Метод теоретического анализа позволил изучить научную литературу по интерактивным технологиям и музыкальной педагогике. В рамках экспериментального метода учащиеся были разделены на группы, обучающиеся по традиционной и интерактивной методике, после чего был проведён сравнительный анализ их знаний, активности и творческих показателей. Педагогическое наблюдение позволило оценить участие учащихся в учебном процессе, их интерес к музыке и творческий подход. В качестве интерактивных методов использовались «мозговой штурм», «кластер», технология «инсерт», ролевые игры, музыкальная импровизация и групповые формы работы. Диагностические и оценочные методы включали тестирование и оценку исполнительских навыков. Кроме того, с помощью анкетирования и интервью были изучены мнения учащихся и преподавателей. Полученные результаты были обобщены с использованием статистического анализа, а также применялся метод рефлексии для оценки самоанализа учащихся.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ И ОБСУЖДЕНИЕ: результаты исследования показали следующее: повышение активности – на уроках с использованием интерактивных технологий значительно возрастает интерес и участие учащихся; прочность знаний – темы, изученные с помощью аудио- и визуальных материалов, лучше сохраняются в долговременной памяти; творческое развитие – интерактивные занятия способствуют развитию самостоятельного мышления, импровизации и творческого подхода; развитие навыков сотрудничества – групповая работа формирует коммуникативные и социальные навыки учащихся. Вместе с тем были выявлены и определённые проблемы: недостаточность технических средств, низкий уровень цифровой компетентности преподавателей и необходимость рационального распределения учебного времени.

ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЕ: проведённое исследование показало, что использование интерактивных технологий на уроках музыки значительно повышает

эффективность обучения. Интерактивные подходы усиливают активность учащихся и способствуют более глубокому и прочному усвоению знаний. Особенно важную роль играют мультимедийные средства и интерактивные методы, способствующие развитию музыкального восприятия, слуха и творческого мышления. Кроме того, интерактивные технологии формируют у учащихся навыки самостоятельного мышления, творческого подхода к решению проблем и применения знаний на практике. Групповые формы работы способствуют развитию коммуникативных компетенций. Результаты исследования подтверждают, что интерактивные методы обучения более эффективны по сравнению с традиционными и повышают мотивацию учащихся. Однако для их эффективного применения необходимо учитывать уровень методической подготовки преподавателей, их цифровую компетентность и обеспеченность техническими средствами. В связи с этим важным является не только внедрение современных педагогических технологий, но и повышение квалификации педагогов, а также создание соответствующих технических условий. В целом использование интерактивных технологий в музыкальном образовании является эффективным педагогическим средством, обеспечивающим всестороннее развитие учащихся.

Ключевые слова: интерактивные технологии, музыкальное образование, креативность, мультимедиа, интерактивные методы, педагогическая эффективность

EFFECTIVENESS OF USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC LESSONS.

Khudayberdiyeva Mushtariy, 3rd-year basic doctoral student at the Qori Niyoziy National Pedagogical Institute of Education, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Annotation

INTRODUCTION: in the context of modern globalization and digital transformation, the use of interactive technologies in the education system is becoming increasingly important. In particular, in music education, interactive approaches contribute to increasing students' engagement, developing their creative thinking, and ensuring effective knowledge acquisition. While in traditional music lessons the teacher played a central role, in lessons organized on the basis of interactive technologies, the student becomes an active participant in the learning process. This makes it possible to develop not only performance skills but also listening, analytical, and independent thinking abilities.

AIM: the main purpose of this study is to comprehensively examine the theoretical and practical foundations of using interactive technologies in music lessons and to scientifically substantiate their impact on educational effectiveness. The study also includes the following objectives: identifying the pedagogical and psychological foundations of interactive technologies and their role in music education; conducting a

systematic analysis of modern interactive methods and tools used in music lessons; determining the role of interactive technologies in the formation of students' knowledge, skills, and competencies; evaluating the importance of interactive approaches in developing students' creative thinking, musical perception, and aesthetic outlook; studying the impact of interactive technologies on students' motivation and engagement; determining the effectiveness of multimedia and digital tools in music education; conducting a comparative analysis of traditional and interactive teaching methods to identify the most effective approaches; assessing teachers' methodological readiness to use interactive technologies; developing scientific and practical recommendations for their implementation; and identifying the role of interactive environments in developing students' independent learning, musical analysis, and creative activity.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: this study employed a comprehensive approach using various didactic and technological materials to determine the effectiveness of interactive technologies in music education. Multimedia tools such as interactive presentations, audio and video recordings, and virtual learning resources were widely used. Technical equipment including computers, tablets, interactive whiteboards, projectors, and audio systems was effectively utilized during the research process. Musical works of different genres, sheet music, and scores served as primary educational materials. Digital platforms, including online learning systems and music applications, were used to organize students' independent learning activities. Empirical data included students' performance recordings, results of classroom observations, and survey responses. Both theoretical and practical methods were applied in the study. Theoretical analysis was used to examine scientific literature on interactive technologies and music pedagogy. Within the experimental method, students were divided into groups receiving traditional and interactive instruction, and their knowledge levels, engagement, and creative performance indicators were comparatively analyzed. Pedagogical observation was used to monitor students' participation, musical interest, and creative approaches during lessons. Interactive methods such as brainstorming, clustering, INSERT technique, role-playing, musical improvisation, and group work were applied. Diagnostic and assessment methods included testing and evaluation of performance skills. Additionally, surveys and interviews were conducted to gather opinions from both students and teachers. The obtained results were generalized using statistical analysis, and reflection methods were used to assess students' self-evaluation processes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: the results of the study revealed the following: increased engagement—students' interest and participation significantly improved in lessons using interactive technologies; knowledge retention—topics learned through audio and visual materials were retained in long-term memory; creative development—interactive activities enhanced independent thinking, improvisation, and creative approaches; development of collaboration skills—group work improved students' communication and cooperation abilities. At the same time, several challenges were

identified, including недостаток technical equipment, insufficient digital competence of teachers, and the need for effective time management during lessons.

CONCLUSION: the conducted research demonstrated that the use of interactive technologies in music lessons significantly increases educational effectiveness. Interactive approaches enhance students' engagement and contribute to deeper and more sustainable learning outcomes. Multimedia tools and interactive methods play a crucial role in developing musical perception, auditory skills, and creative thinking. Furthermore, interactive technologies foster independent thinking, creative problem-solving, and the practical application of knowledge. Group-based learning promotes the development of communication competencies. The findings confirm that interactive teaching methods are more effective than traditional approaches and increase students' motivation and interest. However, effective implementation requires teachers' methodological preparedness, digital competence, and adequate technical resources. Therefore, alongside the introduction of modern pedagogical technologies, it is essential to improve teacher training and provide appropriate technical conditions. Overall, the use of interactive technologies in music education is recognized as an effective pedagogical tool that ensures the comprehensive development of students.

Keywords: interactive technologies, music education, creativity, multimedia, interactive methods, pedagogical effectiveness.

The large-scale reforms implemented in our country during the years of independence have become an important foundation for strengthening national statehood and sovereignty, ensuring security and law and order, the rule of law in society, human rights and freedoms, an environment of interethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and have created the necessary conditions for our people to live a decent life, receive education and careers that meet world standards, and realize the creative potential of our citizens. Based on the new conditions, in accordance with the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and "On the National Program for Personnel Training", the "Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" for 2017-2021, and the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Further Improve the System of Training Pedagogical Personnel, Retraining and Advanced Training of Public Education Workers", it is necessary to ensure the continuity and consistency of educational stages, create a modern methodology of education, improve state educational standards based on a competency-based approach, develop and implement a new generation of educational methodological complexes, and further improve the system of retraining and advanced training of pedagogical workers.

Currently, the State Educational Standards define the requirements for the content and quality of general secondary, secondary specialized, vocational and higher

education. Thus, in music education, the State Educational Standards regulate the elementary foundations of the pedagogy of popular folk music by professional musicians, music performers, great singers, maqomists, and epic poets. The new educational content of music education, based on the State Educational Standards, emphasizes the need to conduct education in them, along with the musical knowledge and skills of students. Therefore, the new content of musical culture education involves raising the younger generation to the level of a cultured person who can inherit our national musical heritage and perceive the universal musical wealth. The main goal is for students to study the art of music with all their might, and for mass music activities: artistic perception of music, singing individually and in groups, dancing, and the formation of creative skills.

What is the educational and upbringing process based on new pedagogical technologies, how does it differ from traditional types of lessons? - we will focus on the question. As is known, in traditional types of lessons, the teacher is at the center of the educational process. He explains, asks questions and evaluates the educational material. Students are weak participants in the implementation process, they are content with observing the teacher's actions. In teaching based on pedagogical technologies, students independently acquire knowledge, skills, and qualifications, while raising their own activities to the level of evaluation. The executor of such teaching is the student. The teacher participates in this as the organizer of teaching and the student's assistant.

In modern conditions of education, there are increasingly serious demands on improving traditional methods and searching for new ones. We all know that currently, advanced pedagogical technologies and non-traditional teaching methods, in particular, interactive methods, are widely introduced into the educational process.

Pedagogical technology is a method of identifying, creating and applying all processes of teaching and learning, taking into account technical means, human capabilities and their interaction in order to optimize forms of education. There are many manuals on modern pedagogical methods of conducting music lessons, such methods were discovered by advanced music teachers themselves and they are giving good results. In particular, the lessons conducted in the form of dialogue, which were conducted in order to find an answer to the natural question: "How much of the topic is remembered and mastered by the student when presented?", show that the independent thinking of today's students is growing as a result of the experiment. We are achieving high results in the process of using interactive technologies for students in music lessons, namely "Mind Attack", "Let's Work in Pairs", "Find Music", "Choose Numbers", "Memory Wheel", "Dialogue" and other methods. It is also effective for students to formulate intellectual questions on the topic and the work before the next lesson, to be able to perform independently. The student should be able to communicate with his peers and teacher on the topic, participate in practical exercises, be able to speak and perform the knowledge he has gained from the lesson, especially to value time, that is, to

think about new sources when given the opportunity, to independently search for ways to strengthen the work, and finally, to be active in the assessment and motivation processes. Only then will the knowledge gained be solidified. The teacher, on the other hand, can study and compare the results obtained during the lesson, think with colleagues, and each can create his own style.

In our republic, the Law "On Education", the "National Program for Personnel Training" and the requirements of the DTS are the basis for the development of vocational education. Based on the program, textbooks, methodological manuals, recommendations, and approximate thematic work plans are being created, because, by the nature of music, along with its ability to strongly influence human emotions, it is an important means of introducing students to the world of elegance, forming musical perception, increasing musical literacy, and moral and ideological education. Strengthening musical perception affects the psychological and physiological feelings of students, ensuring their positive activity. It strengthens memory, attention and hearing, broadens the worldview. The importance of expressive means in the formation of students' musical perception is determined by both the pedagogical and musical professional performance of the teacher in music lessons. If a general idea is given to a performance on an instrument, it is easier to achieve the intended goal. During the lesson, the teacher will provide theoretical information and the main musical path of the work. Listening through technical means in analyzing the topic and musical work accelerates the student's musical worldview and assimilation. In theoretical and practical lessons in music, students must be able to understand general musical terms related to the topic, tune the instrument, play, listen, sing, accompany, perform ensemble and multi-voice musical works. This develops the student's ability to hear, concentrate, and keep in rhythm. The development of such abilities in students leads to an increase in the level of knowledge not only in music, but also in specific subjects. To achieve the effectiveness of the lesson and fully fulfill their professional skills, teachers and educators can achieve their goals through activities based on the requirements of the DTS and new pedagogical technologies.

As we know, music education plays an important role in the development of our society. It carries out the responsible task of educating the younger generation through rare examples of Uzbek musical culture and folk music. Today, lessons should be organized in such a way that the teacher is active and initiative, and his students grow up to be independent and free-thinking young people. Teachers should create a national education system with examples and exhibitions that are relevant to our time and society. If there is a mistake, it is necessary to make corrections in the next lesson or lesson. Our esteemed head of state said, "When we say a healthy person, we mean not only healthy, but also people who have matured in the spirit of oriental morality and universal ideals."

In conclusion, the goal of using interactive, that is, exclusive, methods is to achieve thorough mastery of music by students, as well as to encourage them to be

active, to develop their skills in working together, managing certain situations, and logical thinking.

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